

Freedom From Bondage of Culture in Anita Nair's *Ladies Coupe*

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Abstract

Anita Nair is a contemporary indo-English novelist who has presented the plight of Indian women. Her novel expresses the need of emancipation and education of Indian women. She traces the real position of women in the families as well as in society. The women in the past were completely traditional, uneducated, superstitious and confined. Anita Nair breaks the chains of social norms and do not confine themselves to the boundaries which limit woman. In her novel ladies coupe, she represents the changing image of woman in today's time. Her quest for freedom, self-discovery and self-actualization runs through the novel. All the characters in the novel, try to make some sense of their own existence. The revelation of the five co-passengers leads Akhila towards the path of self-actualization, self-realization, self-discovery and self-fulfillment. Like her fellow travelers, she too determinate to break freedom from all that her conservative life has bound her too. Akhila quests for freedom is turned inward and aimed at the goal of self-discovery. This paper attempts to explore the freedom that the woman characters have got from the bondage of culture in the novel, Ladies Coupe.

Keywords: Emancipation, Confine, Boundaries, Conservative, Freedom, Bondage, Culture.

Anita Nair is considered as a audacious and straight forward writer. Her novels reveal the effect of social conditioning on women. Her novels depict the real life of her characters without hiding anything from her readers. Anita Nair has very nicely, portrayed this concept in her novels. Especially through Akhila in Ladies Coupe.

'**Ladies Coupe**' is a masterpiece by Anita Nair a prolific writer. This novel presents the life of six women, all trapped in the unsteadiness of custom and the social order. It is a story of six women who are in search of autonomy and perseverance. As a woman novelist, Anita Nair depicts the problems of Indian women and probes into their psyche. The protagonist of the novel Akhila breaks out of the traditions of Indian society which chain her. Not only Akhila but also Prabha Devi, Janaki, Sheila, Margaret and Marikolanthu emerge as independent personalities.

The novel, *Ladies Coupe*, follows the journey of a middle-aged Indian woman named Akhilaas she travels from Bangalore to Kanyakumari in her search for independence. On the train's ladies' coupe, she swaps stories with 5 different women – **Janaki**, a pampered housewife's bearing is common to be found in India. **Margaret**, a chemistry teacher represents the women who are forced to lose their self-identity by their husbands. **Prabhadevi** who seeks her identity as a human being not a thing. A fourteen year old girl **Sheela's** portrayal depicts the modern young women who are aware of their need of peculiarity. **Marikolunthu**, pictures the rural women who lose their life because of illiteracy and ignorance. These women inspire Akhila to live her own life. This story also tackles the issues of gender and social injustice that the characters face in their society.

Akhila, who is the protagonist, represents the middle class values of a Tamil-Brahmin family. She is a conservative Brahmin, is determined to break free from the shackles of age-old customs. Marrying one's uncle is an accepted norm in the Tamil-Brahmin community. The independent-minded Akhila at the age of fourteen has no qualms expressing her displeasure and disapproval at her mother's decision to marry her uncle. Further, she strongly opposes her mother's theories on what a good wife ought to be. Her mother's formula of a successful marriage is in subordination of women. Akhila refuses to believe that a woman's need to prove her equality creates strife and disharmony in the house. Her belief in the institution of marriage at the beginning of the novel gradually changes and towards the end of the novel she seduces a young man. A stranger called Vinod in her pursuit of discovering the woman in her. Her awareness of her needs and the self-realization leads to her empowerment. She wishes for companionship as well as motherhood. This is evident in her conversations with herco-passengers when she reveals her innermost desire.

Akhila, the protagonist succeeds in her goal of self-discovery. She succeeds in retaining her dignity even as she finds self-fulfillment. Like the male progeny, she takes over the reign from her father after his death. She rescues her mother from the threat of poverty and degradation. She finds her soul-mate in Katherine Webber as both have no preoccupations with the four corner stones of the grihashthashrama - husband, baby, home, and mother-in-law. Her journey in search of her identity isn't an easy one. It means breaking free from her conservative background.

The ideal Indian woman. Janaki believed that a woman's role was to keep the family intact and reach out to every member. She finds herself in a very agonizing state when forced to bear taunts and derisions at her son's house. Unable to bear the insults, she decides to live with her husband. Her story hints at the dissatisfaction experienced at a certain age by every individual, though what she believes is not true for the women of today's times.

Margaret Shanti, a successful chemistry teacher, is married to an insensitive tyrant called Ebenezer Paulraj. He is insensitive, self-absorbed and different towards his wife. She would like to divorce him, but does not dare to do so because she is afraid of society. With the sole desire of taking revenge on her brutal husband she feeds him and turns him into a fat man. She believes that being fat can erode his self-esteem.

Prabhadevi, accomplished woman married to Jagdish, a prosperous diamond merchant, is quiet and timid to the extent that she has never tried doing anything new. She does not like the way she has evolved and therefore she makes attempts to change herself. Using a swim suit and indulging in swimming gives her a sense of freedom and identity as wife and mother.

Sheela, a fourteen-year old girl. She is a delicate girl who remembers her relationship with her grandmother who has died just then. She is portrayed as a capable girl who can think beyond the ordinary social settings. She dresses up her dead grand mother's body as per her wish.

Marikolanthu, thirty one year old who is a victim of a man's lust. She is poor and uneducated. Her poverty forcing her to do things that violate traditional socio-moral injunctions. Due to her poverty, she has experienced rape, lesbianism and physical torture.

Ladies Coupe deals with a woman's quest for strength and independence. At the end of the novel we realize that every person possess some fine qualities and inner vigor which even they are unaware of. It is only in the face of certain untoward incident or conditions into which they are thrown that these traits begin to surface. Further these qualities receive a finer border and luster only when faced with predicaments. Six women find themselves together in a ladies coupe, traveling, each for her own purpose. This ladies coupe becomes a comfort zone where each one begins voicing their tale and in the process is both assured and persuaded of greater things.

Anita Nair's objective and message is that every woman should seek to find a refuge within themselves, and not elsewhere. Every woman is strong enough to state and as certain that she has a solution to all her problems, instead of being dominated and subordinated by someone. One needs to have a balanced and practical approach towards life and keep working at the wheels of life to keep it going.

During the course of the journey, Akhila gets to know her fellow travelers. All the Characters lead stereo-typed roles, into which women are molded by patriarchal society. They all hope and strive to break free from that mold. When all the five characters meet and share their woes with the protagonist, Akhila, the latter finds the answer to her quest for freedom. Akhila's quest for freedom is turned inward and aimed at the goal of self-discovery.

All the characters in the novel try to make some sense of their own existence by talking about it to anyone who is willing to listen. The revelation of the five co-passengers leads Akhila towards the path of self-actualization, self-realization and self-fulfillment. Like her fellow travelers, she too is determined to break free from all that her conservative life has bound her to. The characters represent the middle and upper middle class, educated, urban woman with the exception of Marikolanthu. The story of Marikolanthu, "a Dalit woman, remains unique and reveals the multiple layers of exploitation she has faced in her life by being a woman, minor, Dalit, and poor. Akhila finally decides to resume her old romantic relationship and take a bold stand in her life" (Niyathi, 107). By liberating oneself from the clutches of family a woman can survive only if she has inculcated in her the culture of self-dependence — both physical and mental.

Akhila represents the New Indian Woman who is dissatisfied with the roles assigned to her by the patriarchal society and manages to reject the cultural/social background totally to transcend the horizons and thus depicting a revolutionary spirit. Anita Nair's heroines negotiate for their independence and a respectable place in society. Anita Nair's heroine is "mentally advanced in the real sense of the world, whether she is Sheela, Janaki, Margaret, Prabha, Marikolundhu or Akila" (Agalya, 3).

The novel also highlights the theme of freedom from bondage of culture, from the concepts of family, marriage and sex as defined by male-chauvinism and are thrust upon women. The protagonist does urge to seek self-fulfillment through self-expression.

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